

IMPORTANCE OF USING GAME METHODS IN ENGLISH

Isayeva Shohsanam Ulugbek kizi

Jahonova Umida Jamolovna

Surkhandarya region Sherabad district school number 3

English teachers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556362>

Abstract. *Since learning foreign languages is gaining importance today, languages are taught not only in higher education institutions, schools, but also in pre-school educational institutions. If the lessons are not taught with unique and interesting methods, it can become a difficult task to attract students to the lesson. If traditional methods are used in the lessons, if they are conducted in an interesting way, this not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but also prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson.*

Key words: *language learning, modern information technologies, pedagogue, student, games, youth psychology, etc.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИГРОВЫХ СПОСОБОВ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. *Поскольку изучение иностранных языков приобретает сегодня все большую актуальность, языки преподаются не только в высших учебных заведениях, школах, но и в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях. Если уроки не проводятся уникальными и интересными методами, привлечь учащихся к уроку может стать трудной задачей. Если на уроках используются традиционные методы, если они проводятся в интересной форме, это не только обеспечивает качество урока, но и предотвращает скуку и привлекает к участию в уроке пассивных учащихся.*

Ключевые слова: *изучение языка, современные информационные технологии, педагог, ученик, игры, психология молодежи и др.*

The role of teaching through various games in teaching English is incomparable. Playing various games during the lesson increases the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom, encourages passive students to better participate in the lessons, and creates an environment of competition and teamwork among students in the classroom. It also increases students' respect for their teachers. Below are games that serve to increase the effectiveness of teaching during English lessons.

There are a number of interesting games in the process of teaching English. It is worth mentioning that when teaching language to children, it is necessary to use such games in which all students participate equally and learn new things from the lesson (for example, new vocabulary can be memorized, if this process is repeated every day, the student vocabulary increases to a higher level). It is inappropriate to start the lesson with grammar concepts, especially for younger students, because it causes them to get bored quickly.

As a result, interest in class may fade. With them, it is even necessary to start the process of greeting in an unconventional way, for example, the method of starting the lesson with an English song about some kind of greeting with the entrance of the teacher (mainly a motivational method for primary school students) is an effective method. If the lesson continues in this way, the students will not lose their attention to one task during the lesson. They even look forward to

English lessons. Of course, all this should be organized by the teacher, and it is the pedagogue's responsibility. Therefore, some types of games can be mentioned to make learning a foreign language interesting. "Rolli games" can be used to improve the effectiveness of English and Russian language lessons. The advantage of this game is that it is played based on the situation. This game is not only useful for learning science, but also helps to develop mental ability. In this game, topics are selected and children create dialogues.

For example, the passenger's conversation when stopping a taxi, or the conversations in clothing stores - all of this is spoken and shown in English. It is in this game that we can use the tactics of working with a group, that is, dividing students into groups and dividing them into different topics. In this case, competition also occurs. Competition is the benchmark. If the group that has done the task well is encouraged, the aspirations of the rest of the students will also increase. In addition, it is appropriate to use didactic games to conduct English lessons meaningfully. OBJECT - this game serves to increase students' vocabulary.

We know that the most important direction in learning a foreign language is to memorize a new word. Taking into account the characteristics of students, each student memorizes vocabulary in his own way. We are sure that memorizing new words through games is suitable for everyone and makes the process easier. In the game we mentioned above, during the lesson, 15 objects in the classroom are placed on the table and the students come and look at these objects. The items are covered and then the students have to write what they see on the board in English for a certain amount of time.

The student who can write the most words correctly will be the winner. In order to ensure the quality of this game, I can say that in order to attract students who are in this situation and did not participate in the lesson, it would be appropriate if they were given the task of making one sentence for the names of these items, and this it also prevents apathy. Pictionary is a game familiar to most English language teachers and learners, a word game with its name and a picture in it. You can use a normal blackboard or a magnetic board to draw in this game. Students of the class are divided into two groups and a table is drawn on both sides of the blackboard for each team. The scores of the teams are recorded in these tables.

Names of words are written on the desk and turned upside down. Pupils from each group take turns choosing one of the hidden words and drawing it on the board. The team that gets it first will be awarded a point. This game also sharpens the minds of students. We can also say that the use of images is a tactic that attracts readers quickly, especially if it is created by the students themselves.

Taboo words game (Forbidden words) is a fun game that helps students use synonyms and their rates. The use of synonyms ensures the fluency of speech and the beauty of speech. Especially in the English language, one should not make mistakes in the use of words, because many words with the same meaning in the English language are used according to the content of the sentence. This game will help you to be careful in this regard. In this, groups are formed, that is, students sit facing each other. Each team chooses one person from their team to sit on the chair opposite them.

The teacher goes behind the students and holds a word written on a large piece of paper. The students sitting in the seats should not be able to see this word. There will be some time for the member of the team sitting in the seat to say the word that the teacher is holding.

Tennis is a game where the goal of the game is to increase the speed of the students. This game is similar to the chain game and takes place within the selected theme. In this case, a new word should be added to the last letter of the said word, for example, if the topic name is "Animals", if it starts with the word "Tiger" without deviating from the topic, the second participant should say "rabbit". he continues. Thus the game continues.

A student who stops during the game and cannot answer within 5 minutes will be removed from the game and will be continued with the rest of the students. Playing the game with a class, that is, with many people, will be very interesting and enjoyable. This game can also be played by changing the theme. At the same time, in the process of organizing games, connecting them with various technical means also serves to increase interest.

Because in today's rapidly developing age, not all young people, teenagers and adults are indifferent to modern technologies. Therefore, it is possible to achieve an effective result by organizing interesting science games on computers.

Bingo - Once students play this game, they will beg to play it again and again! And this game is a great way to make the most of the extra minutes. Ask each student to draw 6 columns on a piece of paper. You can choose a category (topic for a word) from the last visited topics. The most commonly used categories are food, names, cities or countries, furniture or appliances, work or clothes. Choose any letter and write it on the board. Give your students some time to write the words that start with that letter in the columns. You can restart the game as many times as you want with other letters.

In fact, grammar concepts are also taught during teaching, as teachers' lesson plans indicate this. However, there is a game to make this process easier and fun. For example, topic word groups (parts of speech).

They should be able to learn and distinguish word groups well. Students can be given the task of writing only words related to nouns while playing music in English and listening to the song, and then another word group can be given to the student. In this way, the topic is strengthened, this method can be used in the process of passing other topics. It can also be organized as a cultural entertainment for students.

When using games, we can change them depending on the knowledge and age of the children, that is, make them easier or more complicated. The purpose of these above-mentioned games is to strengthen the memory of students, increase their mental capacity, quickness, intelligence, remember new words easily and, most importantly, organize the lesson meaningfully.

Today, the educational process is mainly carried out in a traditional way, but at all stages of the educational system, continuous learning of foreign languages, as well as improving the qualifications of teachers and teaching with modern educational and methodological materials provision requires further improvement. By introducing advanced methods of education with modern pedagogy and information communication, it is desirable to make the growing young generation an expert in the languages they are learning, and on the basis of this, they can speak these languages easily. After all, everything is for the great future of our youth and the development of our country.

REFERENCES

1. Gozcu, E. & Cag anaga, C., K. (2016). The importance o f using games i n EFL classrooms. *Cy priot Journal of Educational Science*. 11(3), 126-135.
2. *Qualitative Research & Evaluation Methods*. Sage Publications. Rixon, B. D. (1979).
3. *Communication Games*. NFER & Nelson for the British Council. Sanchez, M. M. M., Morfin, A. P., & Campos, V. E. P. (2007).
4. Interactive games in the teaching-learning process of a foreign language, *Teoría y Praxis*, 4, 47-66. Silverman, D. (2011).
5. Games for the classroom and English speaking club. *English teaching forum*. Stojkovic, M. K., & Jerotijevic, D. M. (2011).